

TECHNOLOGICAL STRATEGIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING OF INTERNATIONAL JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The demands of the 21st century education have prioritized integrating technology into learning key content areas. In Second Language Learning context, in order to improve language instruction, it is crucial to consider a variety of options in designing programs that would elevate the way students acquire a language. Furthermore, language specialists promote technology-based programs as tools to support students' language development within the school. Having this in mind, the researchers identified a need to assess the students' English proficiency and evaluate the effectiveness of the learning tools used in schools. This study examines the Academic Achievement in English of students at Southville International School and Colleges by analyzing their performance with Southville Academic Technological Strategies (SATS). Data for this research includes students' final grade in English Language Arts, which also includes the TOEFL results, and SATS usage metrics, such as averaged and final scores from Read Theory and Lexile Booktests.

Keywords: *Academic technological strategies, English Language Arts, Academic achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Language learning in the 21st century, with the demands of globalization, initiated significant shifts in the way language teachers plan and deliver instruction to meet evolving learning needs. It is expressed in Begum and Liton (2018)'s reflective paper on needs and demands of 21st century learning skills that as educational systems aim to produce successful and thriving learners in the modern workplace, a rethinking and reshuffling of educational approaches is imperative. Moreover, modern society stipulates the acquisition of 21st century skills beyond acquiring knowledge in situating oneself to the real world (Shadieff & Wang, 2022). Considering 21st century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication, digital literacy has become an emerging aspect of the growing expectations of today's society among learners. Essentially, these grounds call for the integration of modern technology in language learning and instruction.

The progressive use of Information, Communication, and Technology (ICT) in language learning classrooms signals that classes are now beyond four walls, and that digital literacy supports perceived success of students in harboring new sets of skills (Halvorsen, 2018). In the Philippines, technology introduced new learning practices in the already dynamic nature of language learning. Pasternak (2019) suggests that observations be made from practices that cater technology, considering that it is a significant part of the progressive world. With this, educational institutions are geared to accommodate an array of technology-based platforms to facilitate language instruction. Consequently, language teachers were driven to keep pace with progression and with the current trends both in pedagogy and the use of new technologies (Gilbertson, 2007). Teachers in today's time are then aided further by technology-based programs developed by stakeholders to improve language instruction and learning. Vo (2019), through Ferlazzo (2019)'s compilation of responses on ways to use technology in English classes, maintains this by saying that the goal is not to substitute technology to teachers but to seamlessly integrate technology with quality instruction for a meaningful, interactive, and engaging learning environment for students.

Among various technology-based platforms for language learning are programs that screen and evaluate learners' level of language literacy through multimedia, which also has the capability to provide meaningful insight into the personalization of their individual learning experiences. This recognizes that language learning among other major fields of study can be best learned with the use of technology-based materials and equipment (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015). Read Theory, for example, specializes in improving students' reading comprehension through adaptive, engaging, and encompassing passages inclined to the needs of K-12 and English as Second Language (ESL) learners. Similarly, in the secondary level, Lexile Booktests assesses students' reading skills through book assignments and comprehension questions that measure vocabulary, grammar, text analysis, and critical thinking skills. Technology-based assessment tools such as the Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL), a standardized tool also used to evaluate the English-language proficiency of non-native

English language learners and speakers, is inclined towards student success in admission to higher academic setting (college, universities) in the global arena. In an established journal on teaching English for specific and academic purposes, Gunuc and Babacan (2017) emphasize that integrating technology into English language teaching and learning is greatly important in the development of students' listening, reading, speaking, and writing skills. This is further assisted by Shadiev and Wang (2022), saying that language learning from multimedia materials elevates language skills and consequently 21st century skills of students.

Southville International School and Colleges is a nationally and globally recognized academic institution in the Philippines envisioning 21st century successful learners through its offering of internationally benchmarked curricula and learner needs-responsive programs. In the pursuit of developing lifelong learners, it is crucial to recognize that language acquisition in the 21st century is deemed complex and nonlinear, especially that the students acquire, understand, and produce language and communicate it in a variety of forms and purposes (Eaton, 2010). Southville International School and Colleges responds to this complexity by providing its students with data-driven, technology-enhanced academic programs. The integration of technology-based programs in language classes and the commitment to provide the highest quality academic standards to learners concurs with the idea that modern teaching and learning practices are best designed with technology-based tools (Ahmad & Mohebi, 2024).

Southville International School and Colleges utilizes the previously mentioned technology-based programs (Read Theory, Lexile Booktests, TOEFL) in a collective unit known as Southville Academic Technological Strategies (SATS). Given the need to monitor the effect of technology-based program integration to English language learning, this research aims to identify the extent that SATS brings to the level of academic achievement of students of the institution. Particularly, the researchers aim to achieve the following objectives:

- to determine the effect of usage of technology-enhanced learning tools in the English proficiency of the Grades 7-10 students of Southville International School and Colleges;
- to identify the technology-enhanced learning tools mostly utilized by the students; and
- to determine the implications of the technology-enhanced learning tools on the academic Achievement in English of the Grades 7-10 students.

Research Questions

In this study, the researchers seek answers to the following questions:

1. What is the average usage of Southville students of the SATS (Read Theory and Lexile Booktest) provided for them to enhance their language proficiency?
2. What is the effect of the usage of these technology-enhanced tools on the students' language proficiency particularly in their yearend grade in English?

3. Is there an implication on the students' language proficiency when they use SATS more or less frequently?

METHODOLOGY

The present study used descriptive statistics to research. Descriptive statistics was done by computing the average and percentage scores of each of the SATS usage and the students' final grade in English Language Arts Academic Year 2019-2020. Since Lexile Booktests have three attempts, the researchers used the average scores of the first and second attempts since the third attempt is presumed to be perfect.

The research was conducted in Southville International School and Colleges in the south of Metro Manila. The participants were junior (Grades 7-9) and senior (Grade 10) high school students who were enrolled in English Language Arts classes academic year 2019-2020. 368 students from Grades 7-10 were the participants of this study.

Prior to the facilitation of the research, the researchers sent permission letter to the President/CEM, Dr. Genevieve Ledesma Tan, the Principal, Ms. Marie Vic F. Suarez, and the SATS Deputy Principal, Ms. Junessa Lumbres of the private institution. After the approvals, the researchers started the gathering of data. The researchers were given access to the data of the target participants' final grade in English Language Arts, Lexile Booktest, and Read theory. After all data have been provided and completed, the results were classified, tabulated, and analyzed.

The researchers followed the statistical analysis and employed descriptive statistics for data analysis. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to examine the extent and effectivity of the tools in learning and improving the student's Academic Achievement in English.

RESULTS

The present study aimed to conduct an analysis of the SATS on the students' Academic Achievement in English. The data were analyzed based on the results of the averaged scores of the attempts of students' Lexile Booktests, averaged Read theory results, and final English Language Arts grades.

In analyzing the average usage of the SATS (Read Theory and Lexile Booktest) provided to Southville students to enhance language proficiency, the results indicate a high extent of engagement, with a mean score of 836.04 for Read Theory and 78.8090 for Lexile Booktest.

	N		Mean	Std. Deviation
READ THEORY AVERAGE	Grade 7	55	747.82	234.138
	Grade 8	121	783.87	228.470
	Grade 9	144	847.53	228.381
	Grade 10	48	1034.17	192.190
	Total	368	836.04	239.660
LEXILE BOOKTEST AVERAGE OF FIRST AND SECOND ATTEMPT	Grade 7	55	72.5091	26.63392
	Grade 8	121	63.8347	25.83517
	Grade 9	144	96.0347	6.65789
	Grade 10	48	72.0983	31.41052
	Total	368	78.8090	25.85408

Table 1. SATS average usage of Grades 7-10

Based on *Table 1* for the Read Theory Average, 55 students from Grade 7 had a mean of 747.82 with a standard deviation of 234.138. On the other hand, 121 students from Grade 8 had a mean of 783.87, with a standard deviation of 228.470. Meanwhile, Grade 9, which has the most number of students, had a mean of 847.53, with a standard deviation of 228.381. Lastly, Grade 10, the level that has the least number of students, had a mean of 1034.17, and a standard deviation of 192.190. Among these four levels, Grade 9 has the most frequent use of the SATS platform, Read theory.

For the Lexile Booktest, the average scores of first and second attempts made by Grade 7 students had a mean of 72.5091, with a standard deviation of 26.63392. Although Grade 8 has a higher number of students as compared to Grade 7, the former had a mean of 63.8347, with a standard deviation of 25.83517. Since Grade 9 has the highest number of students, they also got the highest mean of 96.0347, with a standard deviation of 6.65789. Lastly, Grade 10, which has the least number of students using the platform, had a mean of 72.0983 and a standard deviation of 31.41042.

As for the effect of the usage of these technology-enhanced tools on the students' language proficiency particularly in their yearend grade in English, the researchers used Multiple Regression Analysis following these assumptions:

- non-zero variance;
- outliers;
- multicollinearity;
- independent errors;
- random normally distributed errors; and
- homoscedasticity & linearity.

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
ELA GRADE (FINAL)	93.25399	4.870436	23.721
READ THEORY AVERAGE	836.48	240.740	57955.875
LEXILE BOOKTEST AVERAGE OF FIRST AND SECOND ATTEMPT	78.8339	25.98738	675.344

Table 2. *Non-zero variance of ELA Final Grade and SATS Result*

As reported in Table 2, the data met the assumption of non-zero variances (ELA Grade (Final), Var. = 23.721; Read Theory, Var. = 57955.875, and Lexile Booktest, Var. = 675. 344).

Residuals Statistics ^a After Removing Outliers					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	82.46970	99.24188	93.25399	3.280939	363
Residual	-11.236640	9.319971	.000000	3.599526	363
Std. Predicted Value	-3.287	1.825	.000	1.000	363
Std. Residual	-3.113	2.582	.000	.997	363

Table 3. *Analysis of Standard Residuals*

As for the outliers, considering the ELA final grade as the dependent variable, an analysis of standard residuals was carried out (See Table 3) on the data to identify any outliers, which indicated that students S229, S242, S245, S246, and S248 needed to be removed. This means that the final ratings of students in their ELA subjects were considered extreme (P). For the data to be considered valid and balanced, the students who got the extreme or no grades (INC) were removed from the list.

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	READ THEORY AVERAGE	.934	1.071
	LEXILE BOOKTEST AVERAGE OF FIRST	.934	1.071

Table 4. *Collinearity Results*

In order to identify if the data met the assumption of collinearity, Table 4 indicated that multicollinearity was not a concern until the final model (Read Theory Average, VIF = 1.071; Lexile Book Test Average, VIF = 1.071).

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.674 ^a	.454	.451	3.609511	1.452

Table 5. Assumption on Independent

As presented in Table 5, the Lexile Booktest Average of First and Second Attempts (constant variables), and the ELA Final Grade (dependent variable) have met the assumption of independent errors as indicated by the Durbin-Watson value = 1.452.

Figure 1. Histogram of standardized residuals

Figure 2. Normal P-P plot of standardized residuals

Figure 3. Scatterplot of Predicted Values

The histogram of standardized residuals as seen in Figures 1-3 indicated that the ELA Final grades and the SATS (Lexile Booktest and Read Theory) results contained approximately normally distributed errors, as did the normal P-P plot of standardized residuals, which showed points that were not completely on the line, but close. Further, the scatterplot of standardized predicted values showed that the data met the assumptions of homogeneity of variance and linearity.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	79.896	.804		99.344	.000
	READ THEORY AVERAGE	.011	.001	.545	13.511	.000
	LEXILE BOOKTEST AVERAGE OF FIRST AND SECOND ATTEMPT	.053	.008	.280	6.954	.000

Table 6. Multiple Rearession Analysis of the data

Furthermore, in order to identify the significance of the SATS usage on the Academic Achievement of the students, using the backward method, it was found that the read theory average ($\beta=0.011$, $t(361)=13.511$) and the Lexile Book Test Average ($\beta=0.801$, $t(361)=6.954$) are positive significant factors of ELA grades (Final) ($F(2, 362) = 149.547$, $p < 0.05$, $R^2=0.454$, $R_{\text{adjusted}}^2=0.451$). (see table 6 for model summary statistics).

This means that SATS usage had a positive correlation with the academic achievement of students in their English classes using the ELA Final Ratings as the basis.

DISCUSSION

The current study aimed to evaluate the impact of the SATS on students' academic achievement in English by analyzing average scores from Lexile Booktests, average

Read Theory results, and final grades in English Language Arts.

Southville students used the SATS (Read Theory and Lexile Booktest) to improve their language skills. The average scores for Read Theory and Lexile Booktest were 836.04 and 78.8090, respectively.

Based on the students' Read Theory averages, Grade 7 had a mean average of 747.82 with a standard deviation of 234.138, based on 55 students. Grade 8 had a mean average of 783.87 with a standard deviation of 228.470, based on 121 students. Grade 9, the largest group, had a mean average of 847.53 with a standard deviation of 228.381. Lastly, Grade 10, the smallest group, had a mean average of 836.04 with a standard deviation of 239.660. Out of these levels, Grade 9 students used the SATS platform and Read Theory most frequently.

For the Lexile Booktest, Grade 7 students had an average score of 72.5091 on their first and second attempts, with a standard deviation of 26.63392. Grade 8, despite having a higher number of students than Grade 7, had an average score of 63.8347, with a standard deviation of 25.83517. Grade 9, which had the highest number of students, achieved the highest average score of 96.0347, with a standard deviation of 6.65789. Finally, Grade 10, with the fewest students, had an average score of 72.0983 and a standard deviation of 31.41042. The data also met the assumption of non-zero variances (ELA Grade (Final), Var. = 23.721; Read Theory, Var. = 57955.875, and Lexile Booktest, Var. = 675.344).

As for the effect of the usage of these technology-enhanced tools on the students' language proficiency, particularly in their yearend grade in English, the researchers used Multiple Regression Analysis following these assumptions:

- non-zero variance;
- outliers;
- multicollinearity;
- independent errors;
- random normally distributed errors; and
- homoscedasticity & linearity.

In order to determine the impact of SATS usage on students' academic achievement, a backward method was used. The analysis revealed that the average scores for Read Theory ($\beta=0.011$, $t(361)=13.511$) and the Lexile Book Test ($\beta=0.801$, $t(361)=6.954$) are positively significant factors for ELA grades (Final) ($F(2, 362) = 149.547$, $p < 0.05$, $R^2=0.454$, $R_{\text{adjusted}}^2=0.451$).

This suggests that SATS usage is positively correlated with students' academic achievement in their English classes, using ELA Final Ratings as the basis.

Conclusions

Through the lens of multiple regression as a tool, the researchers figured out that the SATS usage, specifically Read Theory, an online reading comprehension assessment tool that allows students to read narrative, informative, or informational literary passages, and Lexile Book tests, another assessment tool that measures students' comprehension of the books read assigned according to their Lexile Level, had a significant effect on their Academic Achievement in English.

Grades 7-10 students from Southville International School and Colleges are given these SATS as forms of both formative and summative assessments and are considered integral in providing a global view of students' reading ability. As included in the teachers' instruction and intervention, these SATS target to identify students' weaknesses in terms of reading and comprehension and to improve them through a series of reading assessment tools.

Recommendations

Given the positive effect of the SATS platform on students' English proficiency, continuing the use of Read Theory and Lexile Booktests is advisable. These tools should remain integral to the English Language Arts (ELA) curriculum. The study shows that the use of these tools has a positive and significant impact on students' academic achievement in English. Specifically, the multiple regression analysis indicates that both Read Theory and Lexile Booktest scores are significant predictors of students' final ELA grades. Based on these correlations, it is recommended to further integrate and potentially expand the use of these technology-enhanced tools to support and improve students' language proficiency and overall academic performance in English.

In addition, providing teachers with added training on optimizing SATS tools can help ensure effective use and accurate interpretation of data. Teachers would benefit from workshops on using the features of Read Theory and Lexile Booktests features, as well as on analyzing student progress metrics. Furthermore, implementing a reward system to encourage consistent use of SATS tools could increase student engagement, which may potentially enhance learning outcomes. Most importantly, it is essential to conduct regular evaluations of SATS integration and outcomes. Feedback from both teachers and students must be consistently considered for the purpose of refining the program. Lastly, incorporating additional tools to complement Read Theory and Lexile Booktests is recommended for a more well-rounded approach to language learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the facilitation of the research, the researchers sent permission letter to the President/CEM, Dr. Genevieve Ledesma Tan, the Principal, Ms. Marie Vic F. Suarez, and the SATS Deputy Principal, Ms. Junessa Lumbres of the private institution to conduct the study. After the approvals, the researchers started the gathering of data. The researchers were given access to the data of the target participants' final grade in English

Language Arts, Lexile Booktest, and Read theory. After all the data had been provided and completed, the results were classified, tabulated, and analyzed.

The authors of this study hereby declare that we have fully complied with ethical guidelines in conducting this research. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. We assured all participants of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences or penalties. Additionally, we have taken rigorous measures to maintain the anonymity of all respondents, ensuring that their identities remain confidential throughout the research process and in any subsequent publications or presentations of the findings

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